

Perceptions of Gender Diversity in software development teams

Kelly Blincoe, Department of Electrical, Computer, and Software Engineering, University of Auckland
Olga Springer, Faculty of Electronics, Telecommunications and Informatics, Gdansk University of Technology
Michał R. Wróbel, Faculty of Electronics, Telecommunications and Informatics, Gdansk University of Technology

Technical Report

Survey questionnaire and results

The results of the study are described in the:

Blincoe, K., Springer, O., & Wrobel, M. R. (2019). Perceptions of Gender Diversity in software development teams. IEEE Software.

This study is conducted in cooperation
between the Gdansk University of
Technology and University of Auckland

2019

Survey questionnaire

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Gender-diversity in software development teams

This survey is part of research on the role of gender diversity in software development companies. We invite all female and male members of IT teams, such as programmers, testers, as well as managers, designers, analysts, devops, etc., to take part in the survey. The only condition is the experience of working in gender diverse teams.

It will take about 15 minutes to complete the survey. All questions concern work in the IT team, so give answers based solely on your professional experience. If you have not met a given situation at work, leave the question empty.

Thank you in advance for your time. If you have questions or suggestions about the problem of gender diversity in IT teams, please contact Michal Wrobel.

The research is conducted by Michał Wróbel and Olga Springer from the Faculty of Electronics, Telecommunications and Informatics at the Gdansk University of Technology and Kelly Blincoe from Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering at the University of Auckland.

Survey questionnaire

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Gender

1. Gender (*radiobutton*)
 - *female*
 - *male*
 - *other*

Survey questionnaire

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Gender roles

- *5-point gender scale:*
 - *mostly male,*
 - *slightly male,*
 - *both,*
 - *slightly female,*
 - *mostly female*

Choose for which gender statement fits better:

1. They care more about social relations in the team, like initiating team building activities.
2. They more often set the boundary between work and personal life.
3. They are more emotional.
4. They are favored by the company's management.
5. They help keep the team calm
6. They are better project managers.
7. They are promoted faster in companies.
8. As managers, they are better at motivating subordinates.
9. They find it easier to ask for help.
10. They have a better sense of when to ask for help.
11. They help colleagues of the opposite gender more willingly than they help same gender colleagues.
12. They are more gentle to opposite gender colleagues than they are to same gender colleagues.

Gender diversity

- *Likert 5-point scale:*
 - *strongly disagree*
 - *disagree*
 - *neither agree nor disagree*
 - *agree.*
 - *strongly agree.*

Do you agree or disagree with the following statements:

1. Gender diversity has a positive impact on the product quality
2. Gender diversity has a positive impact on innovation of the team.
3. Gender diversity has a positive impact on productivity of the team.
4. It is positive that more women in IT have emerged in recent years.
5. When teams lack gender diversity, women should be given preference when hiring IT specialists.
6. Giving preference to women when hiring IT specialists is harmful to women.

Survey questionnaire

Gender interactions

- *Likert 5-point scale:*
 - *strongly disagree*
 - *disagree*
 - *neither agree nor disagree*
 - *agree.*
 - *strongly agree.*

Do you agree or disagree with the following statements:

1. Men often misinterpret the behavior of female team members.
2. Women often misinterpret the behavior of male team members.
3. In teams, conflicts between people of the same gender are more common than conflicts between people of opposite gender.
4. I have heard about cases of gender discrimination in the companies in which I worked.

Survey questionnaire

PAGE 4 (only for those who have chosen the female gender)

Questions for women

- *Likert 5-point scale:*
 - *strongly disagree*
 - *disagree*
 - *neither agree nor disagree*
 - *agree.*
 - *strongly agree.*

Do you agree or disagree with the following statements:

1. When joining new team, I established relationships with other female members faster and easier than with men.
2. I feel I have been discriminated based on gender during my IT career.
3. I feel I need to work harder to prove myself compared to my male colleagues.

Survey questionnaire

PAGE 5 (only for those who have chosen the male gender)

Questions for men

- *Likert 5-point scale:*
 - *strongly disagree*
 - *disagree*
 - *neither agree nor disagree*
 - *agree.*
 - *strongly agree.*

Do you agree or disagree with the following statements:

1. I have on first introduction assumed a woman would perform worse than a man based only on her gender.
2. In all male teams there is more internal competition than in gender diverse teams.
3. In gender-diverse teams, the mood is more joyful and cheerful than in male teams.
4. In gender-diverse teams, there is less focus than in all male teams.
5. Men's teams often have a harsh atmosphere (e.g. indecent jokes) compared to gender-diverse teams.
6. It is better to work in a purely male teams.

Survey questionnaire

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Team diversity

How many women should work in your dream IT team?

1. No less than: % (*input*)
2. No more than: % (*input*)

Survey questionnaire

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Personal information

1. Age (*input*)
2. Country (*input*)
3. Professional experience in IT in years (*input*)
4. Roles in IT projects you have held at any time in your career (*checkboxes*)
 - Administrator
 - Analyst
 - Architect
 - Designer
 - DevOps
 - Programmer
 - Product manager
 - Project manager
 - Tester
 - Validation Engineer
 - Other
5. Role in most recent IT project (*radiobutton*)
 - Administrator
 - Analyst
 - Architect
 - Designer
 - DevOps
 - Programmer
 - Product manager
 - Project manager
 - Tester
 - Validation Engineer
 - Other

Thank you!

Thank you very much for taking part in the study. If you want to be informed about the results of our research, please leave your email address. If you have ideas or suggestions on how to encourage women to choose a career in IT, please contact us by e-mail.

1. Email address (*input*)

Survey results

They care more about social relations in the team, like initiating team building activities. (245 respondents)

They more often set the boundary between work and personal life. (244 respondents)

Survey results

Survey results

Survey results
